

Development and improvement of Breast Phantoms with accessible materials

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Abstract— In Brazil, after non-melanoma skin cancer, breast cancer is the type of cancer that most affects women and the one with the highest number of deaths. It is known that early detection of the disease increases the chances of cure and reduces mortality, which is why studies have been conducted to improve the visualization and diagnosis of neoplasms in mammographic images. For the equipment to be properly tested and professionals trained without unnecessary exposure to radiation, the use of simulators, or phantoms, is essential. Considering the difficult access to these simulators, researchers have sought to develop solutions using more accessible materials, as done by Sousa, (2017). The phantom, projected in their work to resemble breast tissue as closely as possible, has layers composed of gel paraffin and PVC films, distributed unevenly to simulate heterogeneously dense regions, according to their concentration. However, it was noted that, over time, the plates showed some deformation and differences in size between one another, resulting in irregular edges when they were superimposed for image acquisition. The objective of this work is, therefore, to reduce the deformation of the layers, using materials that are more resistant than paraffin, and to standardize the shape of the plates, with 3D printed molds, minimizing the irregularity of the edges. To maintain the simulation quality of the previously developed prototypes, the attributes of the images obtained from the phantoms developed by Sousa, (2017), and those produced in this study were extracted and arranged in bar charts to verify their similarity. It was observed that the phantoms made in this work, using beeswax and paraffin, showed high similarity to Angélica's phantom, and are also more resistant to deformation.

Keywords— simulator objects, mammography, breast cancer, plates, texture attributes.

I. INTRODUCTION

Mammography is considered the main test for identifying breast cancer in its early stages, playing a significant role in screening breast neoplasms and also in reducing the number of deaths. The image is formed by a mammography machine,

a specialized device designed for this purpose, which detects X-rays that pass through the structures of the breast tissue in different ways, due to the linear attenuation coefficients and densities that each of them presents [7]. It is a type of exam that requires a high capacity to differentiate breast structures, as they have very similar levels of X-ray absorption, and to identify lesions that can be very small, such as microcalcifications [1].

To ensure that the quality standards of mammography exams are within the requirements of the standards, according to RDC No. 611, of March 9, 2011, i.e., that the images are suitable for analysis and that the radiation dose delivered to the patient is within the established limits, the equipment must be tested, and the professionals working in this area must be trained [6;7]. For this to be done without unnecessary exposure of humans to radiation, objects that simulate human tissue, in this case, breast tissue, are used [9].

Computer-aided detection/diagnosis (CADe and CADx) schemes are used to improve the diagnostic accuracy of mammography. In the development process of CAD (Computer-Aided Diagnosis) schemes, the image processing techniques that comprise them must be extensively tested and validated with a large set of mammographic images representing a variety of case types, including different lesion types and images without mammographic findings, as well as accurate information about lesions and medical reports. However, such image sets are difficult to access. Furthermore, mammographic databases with such characteristics are rare or have limited access, and they generally lack the necessary variability to test the image processing techniques developed for these computational schemes, in terms of lesion specifications and the variety of mammographic equipment, which affects the adaptability of the techniques [8].

Simulator objects, or phantoms, are physical models developed to reproduce the anatomical, structural, and radiographic parameters of biological tissues and thus

provide a rigorous analysis of the interaction of radiation with the human body [5]. The breast phantom, essential for the evaluation of mammography devices, for conducting scientific studies and tests for the use of new technologies in clinical routine, must accurately replicate the anatomy and pathologies of the breast, including details such as microcalcifications and simulated tumor masses [3]. Given the difficulty in accessing these simulators, mainly due to the scarcity of manufacturers and their high cost, researchers have increasingly sought to develop them using inexpensive and easily accessible materials [9], as proposed in the work of Sousa (2017).

The phantom, developed by Sousa (2017), consists of plates (layers) made of gel paraffin and PVC film submerged in gel paraffin, in a non-uniform distribution. This layering, in addition to allowing the acquisition of numerous image patterns, also allows the simulation of different breast densities through random variations in size, shape, contrast, and distribution of lesions. According to the analysis of the images obtained from the arrangement of the plates of different shapes and the comparison with clinical images of real breasts, the materials used in the production presented visual characteristics very similar to real mammograms and, therefore, were considered suitable for use in simulation [1]. However, several irregularities were observed at the edges, which occurred due to the lack of standardization of the size of each plate.

Based on images of Angélica's phantom [1], an image analysis was carried out, comparing the texture attributes of the phantom with real images using Haralick descriptors [10]. The results showed great texture similarity between Angélica's phantom images and real mammogram images [8].

Considering the above aspects, this work aims to improve the Angélica's phantom, minimizing the irregularity of its edges in the image by standardizing the size of the plates with 3D-printed models. It also investigates materials that can replace the gel paraffin used in the Angélica's phantom to simulate adipose tissue. One of the materials tested is beeswax, mentioned in the study by Pinheiro (2024), because, in addition to having radiographic characteristics similar to adipose tissue, it does not deform over time [9].

II. WRITING THE PAPER

It is important to emphasize that the focus of the research so far has been simulating predominantly fatty breasts, since these tissues have linear attenuation coefficients similar to those of gel paraffin, which is the basis of the phantom and the main cause of deformation.

A. Molds

The aluminum foil-coated cardboard mold used in Sousa's (2017) study, although thermally viable, presented several irregularities in its shape and wear after use, directly influencing the shape irregularity. Therefore, in this study, molds with the same dimensions as the previous one were developed, using PLA filament for 3D printing. In addition to the plate production mold, a containment mold was designed with the same shape but without a bottom, to align the overlapping plates during image generation. Both types of molds were developed using Autodesk Fusion software, with dimensions of 9.6 cm x 14.5 cm and a height of 1.8 cm, and a depth of 4.5 cm for the containment mold, as shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1 (a) Mold and (b) Containment mold.

B. Plates

The new plates were made using paraffin gel and beeswax, melted in an oven at a temperature below 100°C (according to their melting points) and poured into a mold 1.5 cm deep, lined with parchment paper to facilitate unmolding. After the materials dried, the plates were removed from the mold and wrapped in a single layer of PVC film to prevent warping over time. The plates were produced using only paraffin, only beeswax, or a combination of both beeswax and paraffin, as shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2 (a) Plates, (b) Plates in the containment mold, and (c) Plates aligned.

C. Image Acquisition

To simulate breasts of different densities, PVC sheets will be inserted in different quantities and shapes among the materials, similar to adipose tissue, as will be done in the next steps. As the plates that simulate density haven't been developed yet, the plates already proposed by Sousa (2017) were used to produce the images, so that the same layout configurations used in his study could be maintained and the characterization and comparison between them could be carried out.

The images were obtained using a SIEMENS mammography unit with Automatic Exposure Control (AEC) mode. The plates were arranged as described in Table 1, where plates from the Angélica's phantom (simulating higher breast densities) and the new plates simulating adipose tissue were combined. It is important to emphasize that the plates from Sousa (2017) have their own names, which were maintained in this study.

Table 1 Phantom configuration

	Sousa, (2017) - Original	This study
Conf. 1	JA + JB + 3 paraffin (P)	JA + JB + paraffin (P) JA + JB + beeswax (CA) JA + JB + paraffin and beeswax (CAP)
Conf. 2	JA + A + 2 paraffin (P)	JA + A + paraffin (P) JA + A + beeswax (CA) JA + A + paraffin and beeswax (CAP)
Conf. 3	JA + C + 2 paraffin (P)	JA + C + paraffin (P) JA + C + beeswax (CA) JA + C + paraffin and beeswax (CAP)
Conf. 4	JA + B + 2 paraffin (P)	JA + B + paraffin (P) JA + B + beeswax (CA) JA + B + paraffin and beeswax (CAP)
Conf. 5	C + paraffin (P)	C + paraffin (P) C + beeswax (CA) C + paraffin and beeswax (CAP)
Conf. 6	Y + paraffin (P)	Y + paraffin (P) Y + beeswax (CA) Y + paraffin and beeswax (CAP)

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The tests consisted of image acquisition using the configurations of Angélica's phantom (original), and the configurations of this study, which involved replacing gel paraffin plates, that simulate adipose tissue, with newly produced plates.

Since the objective of this study is to promote greater uniformity of the Angélica's phantom edges, the density

characteristics of their combinations must also be preserved. Therefore, to assess the similarity between the phantoms produced in this study and the study by Sousa (2017), following the same plate arrangements (six different configurations, as shown in Table 1), 14 Haralick descriptors were extracted, in addition to Skewness and Kutosis. The results obtained were displayed in bar graphs for better analysis and visual comparison. In Figure 3 were presented part of Haralick descriptors.

Fig. 3 (a) Configuration 1; (b) Configuration 2; (c) Configuration 3; (d) Configuration 4; (e) Configuration 5 and (f) Configuration 6.

The graphs presented in Figure 3 show the similarities of the Haralick descriptors between the original images (Sousa, 2017) and the others with the new plates produced in this study. An example of this similarity is shown in Figure 4, where the original ROI and the ROIs with the materials tested in this study for simulating part of the adipose tissue that makes up the breast are displayed.

Fig. 4 Configuration 5 – ROIs analyzed

To evaluate the differences between the descriptors for the ROIs in Figure 4, the ratio between the attributes of the original image and the image with the new plates was calculated for each attribute. In Figure 5, the black line represents the normalization of the attributes for the original image; the closer to 1, the more similar the descriptors are between the images.

Fig. 5 Difference between the descriptors of the new plates and the original one, for Conf. 5.

The average difference between the descriptors obtained for the original image and those obtained for images with the new plates was also calculated, considering the 6 different configurations in Table 1. The results are shown in Table 2, and to facilitate visualization, these results have been converted into percentages and shown in Figure 6.

Table 2 Original and new plates descriptors mean difference in absolute values

	Conf. 1	Conf. 2	Conf. 3	Conf. 4	Conf. 5	Conf. 6
Paraffin (P)	0,0077	0,0238	0,0115	0,0109	0,0524	0,0228
Beeswax (CA)	0,0195	0,0813	0,0062	0,0284	0,0086	0,0127
Paraffin + Beeswax (CAP)	0,0050	0,0273	0,0267	0,0143	0,0108	0,0142

Fig. 6 Mean difference between original and new plates descriptors

The results shown in Table 2 and Figure 6 indicate that the average difference also varies for each plate configuration. Configurations 1 and 6 correspond to simulations of partially and predominantly adipose breasts, respectively. For these configurations, beeswax showed a difference of less than 2%. For the other configurations, beeswax also exhibited low differences, except for configuration 2, where it showed a difference of approximately 8%, the highest among all the comparisons.

In a more detailed analysis (Figure 3), across all plate configurations, the new plates produced solely with gel paraffin, solely with beeswax, and those produced with beeswax and gel paraffin were very similar. It can be concluded from this that the materials tested in the new plates, in addition to simulating adipose tissue, do not alter the texture of the images. Beeswax exhibits the least deformation, proving to be an excellent replacement for gel paraffin (which has lower resistance and is highly flexible). Furthermore, beeswax is a natural, low-cost, accessible, and easy-to-handle material. These characteristics allow the production of highly accessible and reproducible materials.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This study concluded that standardizing the shape of the plates using 3D-printed molds resulted in excellent performance in terms of edge uniformity. Another essential factor was the use of beeswax as a material to simulate lower-density breast tissue, due to its superior performance in mammographic images compared to paraffin, as well as its high practicality, economy, and accessibility. Therefore, in the next steps, new plates made of beeswax and PVC will be manufactured, arranged in different shapes and quantities, so that breast tissue with its various densities can be simulated.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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